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INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AND SYSTEMIC REFORMS IN EDUCATION

Abhilasha Gautam

Research scholar

IGNOU,SOE

Meaning of ICT based education

ICT in education is not a very new terminology. It has now emerged as an information and knowledge guide to make education system more upgrade and updated. There is still common misconception that ICT based education is about teaching students about computer skills. But the fact is this that ICT based education system is about using computer technology as tools to enrich learning in various subjects such as English, science, mathematics etc.

Successful ICT in education consists of:

DIGITAL CONTENT: It is the basic of any ICT based education program. As it works as the very basic building block of an online learning environment. it is a single learning object that is carefully designed to meet a particular intended learning outcome of a specific curriculum or

problem. Now days a lot of digital content is available in the form of format of texts, graphics, animations, audio clips, and video clips and so on.

The information highway cannot be a one way street. Websites need to be created locally, adding new voices to the global conversation and making content relevant to the communities. The first step is language and culture. Digital content at the local level can enhance community participation and institutional transparency.

TEACHERS TRAINING:

It is expected from teachers now to be upgraded with the knowledge of usage of ICT in their classes at every level of education be it in the school or in the colleges. A commitment from the teachers for the continuous improvement of practice is required. During teacher training focus on those things should be done that result in to bring a difference in the student outcomes.

TECHNOLOGY AND NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE:

Education institutes needs to provide computer instant facility in library and classrooms to ensure that the focus stays on those things that make a difference to student outcomes. This is possible only when chances of open access to the technology facility will be given to the students and teachers equally. Computing hardware and software are needed to transform telephone lines into internet connections. Wi-Fi (wire free internet) should be made available in the education institutes.

LOCAL CAPACITY AND COMMUNITY SUPPORT:

community support hereby means open space time, dispensation and support of the community for using the technology. Community should be made aware of using technology for gathering information and sharing ideas like initiatives has done by government in the field of agriculture where special programs have been developed by government. Likewise numerous lectures for distance learners are also telecasted. Benefits of the program can be shared with community by bringing awareness in them about accessing these programs via internet as and when required.

FOLLOWING ARE THE KEY BENEFITS OF ICT BASED EDUCATION

1. It helps in to approach learning by doing approach.
2. It helps in to enable self paced learning.
3. It provides access to wide range of up to date learning material.
4. It enriches learning through a combination of audio, video, images, text and animation.
5. It helps in to enhance learning through interaction and collaboration.
6. It provides a platform that engages students.
7. It helps in to make teaching learning more expressive.
8. It promotes sharing ideas.
9. It provides firsthand experience to the learners.
10. It brings novelty to the already made concepts, ideas and theories.

SYSTEMIC REFORMS AND ICT

In education the terms systemic reforms or systemic improvement is used in reference to

1. Reforms that impact multiple levels of the education system such as elementary middle and high school programs
2. Reforms that aspire to make changes throughout defined system such as district wide or state-wide reforms.
3. Reforms that are intended to influence in minor or significant ways, every student and staff members in school or system.
4. Reforms that may vary widely in design and purpose but that nevertheless reflect a consistent educational philosophy or that is aimed at achieving common objectives.

ICT has affected the modern classrooms at every level as smart boards have taken the place of traditional chalk boards. PowerPoint has made the teaching learning very effective and reflective; ICT has made teachers and students more aware regarding the updates of the curriculum and knowledge.

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ICT in the present era has also widened with the use of mobile technology. Now every class of society have mobile phones with them. Craze of this information and communication technology has risen with tablets, 2G, 3G smart phones or android. Text messaging and social websites like face book, LinkedIn, what sup etc has changed the perspectives of social relations. This reform via ICT has given a new reason for dividing educated from illiterate, men from women, and rich from poor, young from old and urban from rural.

ICT now works like a resource sharing tool. Due to price escalation and budgeting cuts there is a recession and decreasing trend in education sector. Information and ideas can be shared by teachers at every level of school and various departments of university. It has become possible to share the resources of each other by way of consultation, advice, and access to information and subsequently download of information required.

ICT is used in every sector of profession be it teaching, IT, medical, agriculture, finance, marketing or electronics. It Is used in the ever field. Training of this starts from the school education. The power of reasoning and thinking, the ability of judgement and decision making, the sense of human values, the study habits and scientific tempers all are necessary for working in any area and this cannot be achieved without the help of information and communication technology. ICT is relative more economic, effective and easily accessible, it also results in a cost effective and time saving tool. As if some meeting is to be arranged with UN experts it may require lots of funds but it can be easily arranged with the help of technology like SKYPE, It will save the time as well money of both the parties. Such type of Software can be very helpful in systemic reforms of education.

AS A TOOL OF SYSTEMIC REFORM ICT HAS THE POTENTIAL OF

CONCLUSION

The fusion of computing and communications has broken the bounds of cost, time, and distance. It has brought changes to the education system at large. School is the place where the future of the nation flourishes, these schools significantly works to revamp and modernize their educational programs. Though the content, equipment and service cost associated with web based technologies should be taken into consideration by government and proper steps should be taken to make school and society ICT literate.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Chandra,Ramesh,(2010).*universal education and technology in 21st century*. kalpaz publication, Delhi
2. Powar,K.B., Tiwari.M.D.,Dikshit H.P.(2002) *ICT enabled education*. Association of Indian universities, New Delhi

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